

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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SOCIOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT OF MIGRATION PROCESSES

UDK: 316.444.051.63

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Abstract: This article presents a sociological assessment of migration processes in the labor market, particularly focusing on the results of a survey conducted through interviews with both internal and external migrants. The findings highlight the factors influencing individuals to migrate beyond their living spaces, the social conditions of those engaged in work as migrants, the challenges faced by migrants, including social and legal protections, and other identified shortcomings. Scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations for resolving these issues and improving their situation have been developed.

Key words: digitization, digital technology, digital migration, internal migration, external migration, income, social conditions, population welfare, rights, sociology, orderliness, migration adaptability, family, offspring.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mehnat bozorida migratsiya jarayonlariga sotsiologik baho berilgan, xususan, ichki va tashqi muhojirlar bilan suhbatlar orqali o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalariga e'tibor qaratilgan. Natijalarda shaxslarning yashash joylaridan tashqariga ko'chib ketishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar, migrant sifatida mehnat bilan shug'ullanuvchilarning ijtimoiy sharoitlari, migrantlar duch keladigan muammolar, jumladan, ijtimoiy va huquqiy himoya va boshqa aniqlangan kamchiliklar ko'rsatilgan. Ushbu muammolarni hal etish, ularning ahvolini yaxshilash bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamlashtirish, raqamli texnologiya, raqamli migratsiya, ichki migratsiya, tashqi migratsiya, daromad, ijtimoiy sharoitlar, aholi farovonligi, huquqlar, sotsiologiya, tartib, migratsiyaga moslashish, oila, nasl.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена социологическая оценка миграционных процессов на рынке труда, особое внимание уделено результатам опроса, проведенного посредством интервью как с внутренними, так и с внешними мигрантами. Результаты подчеркивают факторы, влияющие на миграцию людей за пределы своего жизненного пространства, социальные условия тех, кто работает в качестве мигрантов, проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются мигранты, включая социальную и правовую защиту, а также другие выявленные недостатки. Разработаны научно обоснованные предложения и рекомендации по решению этих вопросов и улучшению их положения.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, цифровые технологии, цифровая миграция, внутренняя миграция, внешняя миграция, доходы, социальные условия, благосостояние населения, права, социология, упорядоченность, миграционная адаптивность, семья, потомство.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the challenges of adapting labor migrants to a new socio-economic environment remain unresolved. Understanding the values and culture of the country they migrate to, comprehending their rights and obligations, and consequently enhancing economic benefits is highly intricate and crucial for the success of migration.

In the appeal by Sh.M. Mirziyoyev on December 20, 2022, stating, "We are creating necessary conditions for developing our people's skills, expanding their business, supporting internal migration, becoming real entrepreneurs, and generating income," indicates the extensive efforts being undertaken in the field of migration ^[1].

Conducting research using digital technologies in the context of the digital economy on migration processes assists in identifying issues within migration and contributes significantly to their resolution.

It is possible to trace the history of sociological research on migration, especially in the works of D. Massey, in the context of sociology and migration sociology issues intersection over the years. Specifically, in synthetic

migration theory, the characteristics of migrants describing international migration incidents have been distinctly identified [2].

Furthermore, another scholar, E. Lee, delves into the migration issue by delineating various migration factors prevalent in different regions—such as the “pull factor” and “push factor”—indicating the active behavior in operation [3].

Migration's positive impact on the economy has been suggested by J.K. Chen [4]. This suggests that migration contributes more money and better conditions to fulfill economic needs from other countries. However, it also mentions the risk of draining economies in vacant areas due to substantial investments and improved conditions for migrants.

In our research, we conducted a survey among migrant workers currently engaged in labor activities within our country, who previously worked abroad and are now utilizing Cloud technology, to assess their perspectives. The development of our research's following directions enables the evaluation of cities' migration adaptability and the contribution of migrants to the economic development of specific regions:

Firstly, it is essential to identify factors influencing the economic activities of migrants in the labor market.

Secondly, understanding the motivation for migration, i.e., determining why people migrate.

Thirdly, comprehending the role of social networks in making decisions about migration and the nature of migrants' formal and informal interactions with host communities.

Fourthly, gauging the level of entrepreneurship among migrants.

Fifthly, analyzing the engagement of migrants in digital connectivity and virtual labor migration in their home countries.

Sociological studies on migration processes have consistently maintained their significance over time, especially in the urban context, where the economic activities of labor migrants are independently observable. Thus, it is crucial to investigate and emphasize the primary parameters of cities' socio-economic positions in understanding migration adaptability.

The results of research conducted on modern cities' socio-economic conditions, especially concerning the economic activities of foreign labor migrants and the impact of foreign labor migration on our country's economy, can be instrumental.

THE LITERARY ANALYSIS RELATED TO THE TOPIC

Stephen Castles is known for his sociological work that is foundational for scholars worldwide, and it encompasses theories and methods applicable to all societies. Hence, it is evident that his work plays a crucial role in advancing global migration research. However, national development initiatives stemming from historical agendas continue to influence national trajectories. Beyond this, the study of migration is marked by national scientific discourses and hierarchies that have predominantly remained on the periphery [5].

A. Amelina's migration sociology is not narrow or explicitly defined; rather, it is open-ended and multifaceted, engaging in numerous sharp conceptual and methodological debates. These discussions enrich the field of research by constantly transcending boundaries between disciplines, methodologies, migration research, and practices within other social realms, thereby ensuring a continual “boundary-crossing” in three distinct forms [6].

Stepputat F. emphasizes the importance of producing empirical research and analyses on migration for sociologists. Such studies should contribute to contemporary societal understandings. While economic migration research is connected to migration, it involves distinct research topics, methodological issues, and conceptual matters. Analyzing migration as a societal phenomenon where sociological research and social structures play a fundamental role is essential [7].

N.N. Didukh underscores the significant role of labor migration issues and the role of migrants in host society composition in sociological research on migration. This is evident because migration and migrant communities are transforming the social structure of Europe and other regions, introducing social issues and tensions that were inconceivable several decades ago [8].

N.I. Lapshina highlights the necessity of delineating the social status of migrants, indicating that sociological research in the field of migration assists in understanding the social conditions experienced by migrants. The sociological research conducted in the field of migration helps identify the social conditions stemming from the borders of migrant departure and acceptance [9].

Additionally, academics such as Abdurakhmonov K.Kh., Maksakova L.P., Rasulova D., Umurzokov B.Kh., Shoyusupova N.T. have expressed their views on migration. In recent decades, the swift progress in industrial and technological migration has exerted a strong influence on global development and intergovernmental integration processes. The interest of social scientists in investigating migration-related issues has significantly increased.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Our academic research used elements of analysis, synthesis, sociological analysis, comparative analysis, and sociological survey methodologies utilizing interview formats. The study encompassed examination and analysis of migrants' social conditions, social and legal provisions, and various other aspects. The research was focused on migration processes in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In order to clarify these results, we conducted a sociological survey involving 514 citizens who have participated and returned in our research aiming to expand the content of our study and gain clearer insights into migration issues in our country's internal and external migration processes.

For our research purposes, we utilized questionnaire surveys to thoroughly detail the circumstances of each migrant, and conducted interviews with each migrant. Among the participants in our survey, 403 were males, accounting for 78.5%, and 111 were females, accounting for 21.5%. Among them, 150 individuals, or 29.1%, had not moved or had not gone to another place, 333 individuals, or 64.7%, had moved or relocated, and 31 individuals, or 6%, were widows, single parents, or alone.

It is possible from our observations that within our survey participants, women's situations and existences may indicate some positive outcomes:

Firstly, women tend not to leave their homes to seek employment in other regions or districts;

Secondly, the upbringing of their children, the deterioration of education;

Thirdly, women's migration leads to an increase in dependents.

In our online and selected surveys, we identified the origins and destinations of participants in the migration movement. The highest indicators are accurately identified in two regions: Surkhandarya (17.5%) and Kashkadarya (15.6%) (Table 1).

Table 1: Distribution of Participants by Region in Online and Offline Surveys¹

Which region are you from	Quantity	Percentage
Republic of Karakalpakstan	20	3,8911
Andijan	39	7,5875
Bukhara	29	5,642
Jizzakh	25	4,8638
Kashkadarya	80	15,564
Navoi	11	2,1401
Namangan	19	3,6965
Samarkand	42	8,1712
Surkhandarya	90	17,51
Syr Darya	34	6,6148
Tashkent region	36	7,0039
Ferghana	29	5,642
Khorezm	18	3,5019
Tashkent city	42	8,1712

Based on the information from Table 1, it can be said that in almost all regions participating in migration, Surkhandarya (17.5%) and Kashkadarya (15.6%) regions have the highest population migration rates, followed by Samarkand region (8.1%), Tashkent city (8.2%), Andijan region (7.5%), Tashkent region (7%), Syrdarya region (6.6%), and in other regions, migration processes are observed.

In our research, we observed that migrants from certain age groups, that is, which age groups of citizens tend to be more involved in migration (see Figure 1).

¹ Formulated based on the survey results by the author.

Figure 1: Distribution by age of participants involved in online and questionnaire surveys.

The age range of migrants depicted in this picture primarily comprises individuals aged between 30 and 39 years, who constitute a significant portion of the migrating population. One of the primary reasons for this higher migration within this age bracket could be explained by the economic needs of the family. Additionally, migration tends to be relatively higher among women in this age group.

Moreover, it's worth mentioning that among the participants, 170 individuals (33%) were highly educated, 162 individuals (31.5%) possessed intermediate-specialized education, 159 individuals (30.9%) had intermediate education, and 23 individuals (4.5%) had incomplete intermediate education.

The findings of the conducted survey suggest that in families of most migrant workers, having either no children or two children is more prevalent (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of the number of children among migrants participating in online and survey questionnaires

In conclusion, it is possible to observe that 33% of migrants find smaller family sizes reasonable due to economic difficulties, while 26% have regulated their family size to two children in each family. From a positive perspective, these indicators might be linked to a decrease in the youth population. Thus, the economic sustainability of a family plays a significant role in determining family planning decisions.

Figure 3: Distribution of migrants participating in the online and sample survey by specialty²

Figure 2 shows that many migrants are primarily specializing in pedagogy. Considering the level of information emphasized earlier, we might assume that it is related to the level of education. If we consider that the proportion of higher education among migrants is equal to 33%, it might suggest that not all migrants possess higher education qualifications. Among migrants, 23% are educators, 18.2% are in the construction specialization, 7% are economists, accountants, and others.

Table 2: The indicators of the participants' digital literacy in the online survey and questionnaire³

Are you currently employed in an official or unofficial capacity?	Quantity	Percentage
Yes, officially employed	150	29,183
Yes, unofficially employed	189	36,77
I am not employed	130	25,292
Formally unemployed	45	8,7549

In our survey, the official employment rate among migrants constitutes 29.2%. The unofficial employment rate is 36.7%, and I am not employed in either an official or unofficial capacity, indicating 25.3% and 8.8%, respectively.

Figure 4 shows that migrants going to other countries are coming as undocumented workers (22.1%). This may indicate several issues: labor rights, job insecurity, and when labor conditions are informal, nobody guarantees them, which may lead to unfair treatment and possible exploitation.

Analyzing the causes of informal employment and whether or not they work in formal jobs, it was determined that 25.0% of participants were worried about low monthly income jobs, and 20.1% of mid-level informants were not working in formal jobs. Consequently, it is clear that there is a need to consider the amount of low-wage work when creating vacant jobs in our country and that the low level of monthly income is determined by the economic situation of the region.

A portion of internal migrant workers in informal employment, nearly 15.2%, approximately 2-2.5 million people, indicated the receipt of low-wage jobs and lack of job conditions (8.7%). The quantity of informal employment may further increase in the regions. Therefore, there is a trend in the population towards migration.

² Formulated based on the survey results by the author.

³ Formulated based on the survey results by the author

Figure 4: Indicators of the involvement of migrants in which field in online surveys and interviews⁴

In the current information age, if we look at migrants' usage of digital resources as an indicator, it gives us the following results (Table 3).

Table 3: The rate of using digital technologies by migrants⁵

Do you use digital technologies (computer, phone, tablet) for job searching?	Quantity	Percentage
Yes	219	42,607
No	245	47,665
I don't use digital technologies	50	9,7276

9.7% of the survey participants not being able to use resources in general might be related to their age indicators. In the survey, those aged 40-49 and 50-60 constituted 13.6% and 3.7%, respectively. These age groups may use traditional methods more frequently for accessing information about vacant job positions online, directing their inquiries to organizations searching for job opportunities.

Considering that the primary part of migrants facing informal employment and those migrating for temporary jobs do not apply to state responsible institutions or Employment Assistance Centers (EAC) with a request (Table 4).

Table 4: The number of individuals who applied to assistance centers for employment support⁶

Have you applied to the employment support center? If you have applied, what is your opinion about the center's activities?	Quantity	Percentage
Yes, excellent.	42	8,1712
Yes, average	83	16,148
Yes, quite well	71	13,813
Yes, not very well	78	15,175
Yes, impractical at all	45	8,7549
No	166	32,296
I'm not aware of such a center	29	5,642

4 Formulated based on the survey results by the author

5 Formulated based on the survey results by the author

6 Formulated based on the survey results by the author

Out of the observed migrants, 32.3% did not complain to Migration Support Centers (MSCs) about their living conditions, while among those who did, 15.1% expressed dissatisfaction, and 5.6% were unaware of such centers. The involvement of migrants in seeking support indicates a significant situation. Research findings reveal that the recommended job opportunities did not match their expertise, and there was a shortage of suitable job positions.

In the 5th graph, regarding the migration of individuals from areas with high population density to those with low population density, the following preferences were expressed: firstly, 207 individuals or 28.2% suggested job placement based on expertise, secondly, 191 individuals or 26.0% proposed the necessity of facilitating employment for family members, and thirdly, 144 individuals or 19.6% expressed their preference for internal migration under certain conditions, signaling their approval of internal migration and reduced engagement in external labor migration.

Figure 5: Providing employment through internal local migration⁷

At present, the number of citizens in our country who intend to emigrate abroad comprises 356 individuals, which is 69.2% of the total surveyed population. Some of the highly informed citizens participating in the survey also express their willingness to migrate for foreign employment. Being highly informed includes indicating a desire to work abroad.

Out of those participating in the survey, 235 individuals, or 45.7%, indicated working as labor migrants in foreign countries, while 237 individuals, approximately 46%, highlighted being internal migrants, facing either formal or informal barriers in the capital city. Hence, for internal migrants, the city of Tashkent appears as an example where employment opportunities might be available.

Those aspiring to become migrants indicated the following primary reasons for seeking work in other provinces or countries (Table 5).

Table 5: Migrants' main reasons for engaging in labor activities in foreign countries⁸

List a few reasons why you desire to work abroad (if applicable)	Quantity	Percentage
higher monthly wages	283	26,876
better working conditions	124	11,776
ease of finding employment	81	7,6923
the advice of acquaintances	53	5,0332
The absence of well-paying jobs in the place of residence	82	7,7873
Not being paid on time at work	21	1,9943
Urgent need to gather money for a wedding	32	3,0389
Urgent need to gather money for my wedding	17	1,6144
Urgent need to gather money to buy a house or apartment	84	7,9772
Acquiring a vehicle or other property	54	5,1282
For the initial capital to start my own business	80	7,5973

⁷ Formulated based on the survey results by the author

⁸ Formulated based on the survey results by the author

To repay debts	38	3,6087
Inadequate living conditions for my family	39	3,7037
The lack of adequate social infrastructure development	34	3,2289
others	31	2,8

Based on the information in Table 5, it is evident that the primary incentive for migration is an economic factor, namely monthly income (26.9%), playing a significant role. Following this, the availability of job opportunities (11.8%), the urgent need for quick money to buy a house or apartment (7.9%), lack of well-paying jobs in the place of residence (7.8%), the desire to start a business (7.5%), and other reasons have been indicated.

A majority portion of migrants, 17.7%, considers employment in the USA acceptable (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Main destination countries appealing to migrants⁹

Figure 7: The required amount of monthly wage for migrants to engage in labor activities within their own region¹⁰

9 Formulated based on the survey results by the author

10 Formulated based on the survey results by the author

From the image, it is evident that a large portion of those expressing a desire to work abroad have indicated the USA (17.7%), Germany (14.1%), Turkey (12.3%), European countries (10.6%), and other countries as their preferred destinations. The main reasons highlighted for this preference are the high wages, availability of job opportunities, and ease of finding employment.

Interestingly, 56.6% of migrants are unaware of the labor laws and skill requirements of the countries they aspire to, while 32.1% have confirmed having some knowledge. Lack of knowledge about labor laws and requirements in foreign countries often leads to several issues in the workplace for migrants. Individuals who have been engaged in labor activities abroad have reported an average monthly income of 700 US dollars, obtained through formal or informal means [9].

Migrants, in order to engage in labor activities while living with their families without participating in the migration process within their regions, estimate that 35% of migrants find a monthly income of 2.5 million soums sufficient, while 16% consider 3 million soums monthly as adequate. Therefore, the inadequacy of monthly wages in regions is also a significant factor contributing to migration.

As a result of the survey, migrants have proposed the following recommendations for effective management of labor migration (Table 6).

Table 6: Suggestions for organizing labor migration effectively ¹¹

Your suggestions for effectively managing labor migration in Uzbekistan? (You can choose several)	Quantity	Percentage
Creating new professions that provide advice for working abroad	98	12,312
Increasing international agreements by the state to send citizens to developed countries for employment opportunities.	213	26,759
Developing online platforms to effectively provide social-economic support for citizens working abroad.	155	19,472
Simplifying and digitizing the process of obtaining necessary documents for working abroad	112	14,07
Assisting in ensuring timely payment of labor rights for citizens working abroad	84	10,553
Enhancing restrictions on online labor migration	120	15,075
Developing guidelines for using digital tools	14	1,7588

The table indicates that a majority of migrants propose the increase of international agreements by the state to send citizens to developed countries for employment opportunities (26.8%), ensuring effective social and legal protection for citizens working abroad (19.4%), establishing advisory centers in each district and city to provide guidance on working abroad (15.0%), and several other suggestions.

In conclusion, it is essential to emphasize that in Uzbekistan, the transformation of labor market migration processes, in line with the creation of new professions and the development of a digital economy, aims to facilitate digital transformation in the labor market. This involves:

Establishing a system based on legal protection to create new types of employment and protect digital labor rights.

Expanding high-tech sectors for economic sustainability, increasing the number of technological channels, attracting labor resources to those channels, expanding the information system's operation, and considering changes in the labor market in urban and rural areas to enhance labor resource competitiveness and foster professional mobility.

Implementing measures to regulate labor markets and control population mobility outside their usual place of residence to reduce the number of job seekers and regulate labor and population management agencies to create new sustainable job positions.

Improving the expertise of returning specialists who have developed experience and skills in high-tech sectors in developed countries and enhancing their contribution to innovation and sustainability in national production after their return.

Strengthening collaboration in regulating labor migration with digital and virtual labor migration in the labor market.

Advancing research using cloud technologies to foster innovation.

Currently, virtual labor migration and digital labor concepts are gaining momentum. Organizing free courses to engage citizens in using digital technologies and developing new types of labor and integration with labor activities will be fundamental in managing population migration and employment dynamics.

¹¹ Formulated based on the survey results by the author

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